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Review Article

REVIEW STUDY: MANAGEMENT OF ALLERGIC RHINITIS

Khalid A. Alshehri¹, Ahlam Misfer Saad Alqahtani², Batool Mesfer Mohammed Alqahtani², Mona Ali Saleh Alqarni², Rasha Saeed Mohammed Alqahtani², Shatha Saeed Mohammed Alqahtani², Waad Abdulrahman Saad Al-nahi²
¹ORL-NHS Consultant, ²King Khalid University

Article Received: July 2019**Accepted:** August 2019**Published:** September 2019**Abstract:**

Allergic rhinitis is a worldwide chronic health disease with high prevalence and associated with negative impact on the quality of life. The treatment of AR is challenging thus this literature review provides a summary on the proper management and control of allergic rhinitis. Unfavorably susceptible rhinitis is a typical issue that can altogether affect quiet personal satisfaction and impair the quality of life. The conclusion is made through a complete history and physical assessment. Further symptomatic testing utilizing skin-prick tests or allergen-explicit IgE tests is normally required to affirm that hidden sensitivities cause the rhinitis. The helpful choices accessible for the treatment of allergic rhinitis are successful in overseeing indications and are commonly safe and well-endured. Second-age oral antihistamines and intranasal corticosteroids are the pillar of treatment for the turmoil. Allergen immunotherapy just as different drugs, for example, decongestants and oral corticosteroids might be helpful in select cases.

Keywords: Allergic rhinitis, quality of life, diagnosis, treatment, control.**Corresponding author:**

Khalid A. Alshehri,
ORL-NHS Consultant.

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INTRODUCTION:

Allergic rhinitis is a worldwide chronic health disease with high prevalence among 15 -20 % of general population [1, 2]. It is associated with negative impact on the quality of life, work and sleep quality [3-5]. AR can interfere with the cognitive and social behavior resulting in impairing the social and psychological states. However, the condition is noncontagious, but it is still a serious problem due to the high prevalence and impact on the quality of life [6].

AR symptoms can reveal spontaneously or be treated with drugs including itching, sneezing, rhinorrhea, and nasal obstruction [7, 8].

It is also associated with a socioeconomic burden on the government, society, and care givers [9] and the European Union [EU] has prioritized the importance of allergic rhinitis management, control and prevention [10, 11].

The treatment of AR is challenging to treat as different phenotypes have been emerged and the patients admitting to physicians usually suffer from moderate to severe types [12]. Recently, many treatments are available for AR according to the severity and the phenotype of the disease [13].

The management must consider the gaps between the pathogenesis and etiology of the disease with the pharmacological and control-assessment advances [14]. This literature review provides a summary on the proper management and control of allergic rhinitis.

Allergic rhinitis management:

Rhinitis is a common respiratory disorder however it is not a life-threatening condition but it can decrease the quality of life and result in many socioeconomic impacts [14, 15]. The first step of management is early and proper diagnosis followed by complete investigation and making the decision of accurate treatment.

Diagnosis and investigations

Allergic rhinitis is typically a chronic condition that is regularly undetected at hospital's primary care facilities. Patients experiencing this condition regularly neglect to perceive the effect of the disorder on personal satisfaction, quality of life and working ability and, subsequently, don't oftentimes consider therapeutic management. Likewise, doctors neglect to normally interrogate patients regarding the disorder during the regular visits [15]. Thus, screening and investigating for rhinitis is suggested, especially in asthmatic patients

as researchers have presented that rhinitis is prevalent among 95% of asthmatic patients [16].

An intensive history and physical assessment are the foundations of setting up the determination of allergic rhinitis. Hypersensitivity testing is likewise significant for affirming that fundamental sensitivities cause the rhinitis thus there's need for admitting to an allergist if AR is suspected [17].

History

History taking from patients will frequently depict the accompanying great side effects of unfavorably allergic rhinitis as nasal clog, nasal tingle, rhinorrhea and wheezing. Hypersensitive allergic conjunctivitis of the eye is also related with unfavorably susceptible rhinitis and side effects for the most part incorporate tearing, redness and tingling of the eyes [18, 19].

The history must evaluate the patient's home and environment. Also, it must include the use of medications, allergens, using over the counter drugs and family history.

Physical examination:

The physical assessment of patients who are supposed to suffer from hypersensitive rhinitis ought to incorporate an evaluation of outward signs [mouth breathing blockage, nasal wrinkle], the nose, ears, sinuses, back oropharynx. Assessment of the nose normally uncovers swelling of the nasal mucosa and pale, slight emissions. An interior endoscopic assessment of the nose ought to likewise be considered to evaluate for auxiliary variations from the norm including septal deviation, nasal ulcerations, and nasal polyps [5, 17, 20]. Examination of the nose typically reveals swelling of the nasal mucosa and pale, thin secretions. An internal endoscopic examination of the nose should also be considered to assess for structural abnormalities as nasal septal deviation, ulcers, and polyps [18, 21, 22].

The sinus assessment ought to incorporate palpation of the sinuses for proof of delicacy or using a tongue depressor to tap of the maxillary teeth for proof of allergy.

Diagnostic tests:

In spite of the fact that an exhaustive history and physical assessment are required to set up the clinical finding of rhinitis, further demonstrative testing is important to affirm that basic hypersensitivities cause the rhinitis. Skin-prick testing is viewed as the essential

technique for recognizing explicit unfavorably susceptible triggers of rhinitis[5, 15, 23].

Treatment:

The treatment objective for unfavorably susceptible rhinitis is alleviation of symptoms. Remedial choices accessible to accomplish this objective incorporate intranasal corticosteroids, avoidance measures, oral antihistamines, nasal saline irrigation, combination intranasal corticosteroid/antihistamine sprays; leukotriene receptor antagonists [LTRAs], and immunotherapy for allergens. Different treatments that might be valuable in select patients incorporate decongestants and oral corticosteroids[24].

Allergen avoidance:

The primary line treatment of unfavorably susceptible rhinitis includes the shirking of significant allergens as dusts, pets, parasites and molds, and aggravations. Patients adversely affected by house dust bugs ought to be told to utilize allergen-impermeable spreads for bedding and to keep the humidity and moistness in the home underneath half to repress parasite development. Dust and open-air form presentation can be decreased by shutting the windows, utilizing channels for window screen, utilizing a forced air system, and restricting the measure of time spent outside during pinnacle dust seasons[5].

As for the patients oversensitive to pet dander, getting rid of the animal from the house is prescribed and generally brings about a huge decrease in side effects during 4–6 months. Although, consistence with this suggestion is poor and, consequently, the utilization of high-effectiveness particulate air [HEPA] channels and confining the pets from the room or to the outside might be expected to endeavor to diminish allergen levels. Measures for diminishing introduction to shape allergens incorporate cleaning with fungicides, decreasing the humidity to under half, remediation of any water harm, and using filtration. These management and avoiding systems can successfully improve the manifestations of unfavorably allergic rhinitis, and patients ought to be educated to utilize a blend with respect to measures for ideal outcomes [25, 26].

Intranasal corticosteroids:

Intranasal corticosteroids are considered as first-line remedial choices for patients with mild persevering or moderate/serious signs and side effects of AR and they can be utilized alone or in blend with oral antihistamines. At the point when utilized routinely and accurately, intranasal corticosteroids viably diminish

aggravation of the nasal mucosa and improve mucosal function. Some studies have demonstrated that intranasal corticosteroids are better than antihistamines and leukotriene receptor for monitoring the side effects of hypersensitive rhinitis, including nasal clog, and rhinorrhea [27]. Above that, they improved the visual symptoms and decreased lower airway manifestations in patients with simultaneous asthma and unfavorably AR [28, 29].

Preferably, intranasal corticosteroids are drug of choice to start medication only before presentation to pertinent allergens and ought to be utilized consistently since their pinnacle impact may take a few days to initiate[30].

It is critical to take note of that majority of patients with AR exhibiting to their essential consideration doctor have moderate-to-serious manifestations and will necessitate administration of intranasal corticosteroid. One the same consistence, an improvement was detected among patients with moderate-to-extreme symptoms who were treated with a mix of these remedies[31].

Antihistamines:

Oral histamines are the primary line medications prescribed for all patients with allergic rhinitis. The second generations of antihistamines were detected to adequately lessen wheezing, tingling, sneezing and rhinorrhea if used consistently at the season of maximal warning sign or before presentation to an allergen. Although the first generation [original] calming antihistamines are additionally viable in alleviating side effects as they have been appeared to contrarily affect insight and working, cognitive behavior thus they are not regularly suggested for the management of allergic rhinitis[32-34].

On the off chance that intranasal corticosteroids are not compelling, a blend of corticosteroid/antihistamine spray could be attempted[35, 36].

Leukotriene receptor antagonists:

The Leukotriene receptor opponents [LTRAs] including zafirlukast and montelukast are determined to be viable in the management of AR but they don't give off an impression of being as compelling as intranasal corticosteroids [37]. Also, longer-term studies have observed the efficiency of intranasal corticosteroids than the mixture of LTRAs with antihistamines for decreasing nasal side effects [38, 39]. Even though one transient research found that the mixture of LTRAs and

antihistamines could be used as compelling as intranasal corticosteroids [40]. It is essential to know that that in Canada, montelukast is the main LTRA of choice shown for the treatment of AR among grown-ups.

LTRAs ought to be taken into consideration when oral antihistamines, intranasal corticosteroids as well as blend corticosteroid/antihistamine splashes are not very much endured or are inadequate in controlling and monitoring of AR symptoms. If the combined pharmacological treatment mixture with oral antihistamines, intranasal corticosteroids, mix corticosteroid/antihistamine splashes and LTRAs isn't successful or isn't endured, at that point allergen immunotherapy ought to be measured[41, 42].

Allergen immunotherapy:

Allergen immunotherapy includes the subcutaneous way of steadily expanding amounts of the patient's significant allergens till the successful dose is accomplished to establish immunologic resistance to the allergen. It is a powerful treatment for AR, especially for patients with irregular [occasional] hypersensitive rhinitis that caused by dusts or pollens [33, 43, 44]. It has been demonstrated to be successful for the treatment of unfavorably AR due to house dust bugs, *Alternaria*, cockroach, and feline and canine dander. Allergen immunotherapy ought to be held for patients in whom ideal preventive measures and pharmacotherapy are deficient to control side effects or are not very much endured[45].

Proof recommends that the immunotherapy should be used for at least to 3 years to achieve valuable impacts in patients with allergic rhinitis that can continue for quite a long while after end of treatment[46]. Immunotherapy may likewise decrease the hazard for the future advancement of asthma in kids suffering from hypersensitive rhinitis [44-48].

Likewise, the sublingual immunotherapy is a method for desensitizing patients[43]. The sublingual course of immunotherapy suggested different potential advantages over the subcutaneous course including the solace of evading infusions, the comfort of home organization, and a good wellbeing profile. Like subcutaneous immunotherapy, sublingual immunotherapy is presented for those with hypersensitive rhinitis who have not reacted to or endured traditional pharmacotherapy[48].

Since this type of treatment conveys the risk of anaphylactic responses, it should be prescribed only by efficient physicians[46].

Complementary and alternative medicines [CAM]:

As for the prevalence of Complementary and alternative medicines [CAM] in the overall public, it is sensible for doctors to get some information from patients about their utilization of CAM in an indulgent way. There is a lack of the set number of well-structured clinical researches looking at the adequacy of CAM in AR management which makes it hard for clinicians to assess these treatments and give proper direction of usage. In any case, as long as there will be patients who seek after CAM for the administration of hypersensitive rhinitis, it is prudent to give some data about these treatments including a dialog of the investigations assessing a portion of these treatments[49, 50].

Different CAM have been utilized for the administration of allergic rhinitis, including conventional Chinese medicaments, needle therapy, homeopathy, and natural treatments with herbs and their extracts [51]. In various investigations, acupuncture or needle therapy has been presented to give unassuming advantages to patients with allergic rhinitis [52, 53].

CONCLUSION:

Allergic rhinitis is a typical issue that can altogether affect quiet personal satisfaction and impair the quality of life. The conclusion is made through a complete history and physical assessment. Further symptomatic testing utilizing skin-prick tests or allergen-explicit IgE tests is normally required to affirm that hidden sensitivities cause the rhinitis. The helpful choices accessible for the treatment of allergic rhinitis are successful in overseeing indications and are commonly safe and well-endured. Second-age oral antihistamines and intranasal corticosteroids are the pillar of treatment for the turmoil. Allergen immunotherapy just as different drugs, for example, decongestants and oral corticosteroids might be helpful in select cases.

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